

Endocrown a New Era of Post Endodontic Restoration

Case 1

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A case of ceramic endocrown. A 35 year old patient reported to our conservative department with chief complaint of dislodged restoration in relation to 36. On clinical inspection the restoration was dislodged and tooth was already root canal treated. On further evaluation we concluded to reinforce tooth with post endorestitution ENDOCROWN. The fine grit wheel bur was used for occlusal reduction 2 mm in axial direction by directing the bur along long axis of the tooth and held parallel to occlusal surface. This provided a flat surface and determined the position and placement of cervical margin. Supragingival finish line was chosen. Pulp chamfer was prepared by giving liner of gic light cure. All undercuts should be blocked. Walls of pulp chamber were prepared parallel to each other and checked with GP stick. Silicone impression was taken and bite was also recorded. Die was prepared and fabrication of Endocrown was made after Shade selection. The Endocrown was fabricated from lithium based ceramic by injecting the melted ceramic pellet into a lining mould which was done after wax up. Firing temperature was 850 degree centigrade. The final appointment of patient comprised of removing temporary and luting the Endocrown with dual cure luting cement.

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Pre operative picture showing root canal treated tooth

After Cutting 36

Impression of Endocrown in 36

Die preparation in relation to 36 for Endocrown

Endocrown

Endocrown in situ 36

Anterior Esthetic Fibre Splint

Case 2

Pre operative photograph of patient. Anterior teeth were one degree mobility and Vitality response was normal.

Fibresplint Done. Post operative photograph. The patient reported to the OPD with chief complain of mobility in anterior teeth. He had history of fall from bike a week before. On clinical examination the patient anterior teeth were one degree mobile but were vital and showed no signs of inflammation. Vitality response was normal. Thus a fibre splint was planned. Surface of tooth was cleaned and etched and bonded and splint was cut according to requirement and pressed against teeth with composite in place on each .

